

Morphing Skins Based on Curved Origami with Programmable Stiffness

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Outline

- **Background**
- **Periodic Miura-Origami monocytes**
- **Non-periodic Miura-Origami monocytes**
- **Conclusions**

Background

- The morphing aircraft changes its shape in real time according to different flight missions and flight environments to obtain optimal aerodynamic performance.

NASA: the 21st Century Aerospace Vehicle

Morphing strategy and flight performance envelopes

How to develop morphing skin technology?

- Load-bearing performance : high out-of-plane stiffness
- Deformation performance: low in-plane stiffness

Background

- The aerodynamical performance of morphing winglet were calculated and the results show significant benefits .

Winglet Vortex Reduction Example

Payloads	+30%
Pneumatic efficiency	+3%
Voyage	+5%
Max Cl	25%
Cd	-4%
sliding distance	-20%

Background

- Rigid skin and flexible skin have their own advantages.
- Miura Origami skin integrates both their advantages.

Rigid skin

- High load-bearing capacity
- Rough surface, poor deformability

Flexible skin

- Smooth and continuous, high deformation capacity
- Weak load-bearing capacity

Miura Origami

Integrate
deformation
&
load-bearing

- Anisotropic
- Large deformation
- High specific strength

Background

- Origami is an emerging **interdisciplinary** science that integrates mathematics, mechanics, materials and other science.
- It can transform from two-dimensional **flat sheets** to three-dimensional **complex structures** by predetermined folds.
- It has **excellent mechanical properties**.

Miura-Ori

Huffman Origami

Yoshimura Origami

Barreto Origami

(a) Folding sequence simulated in MATLAB

(b) Folding sequence of card prototype

Curved origami with different folding levels

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 - Straight configuration Miura-Origami analysis
 - Arc configuration Miura-Origami analysis
- **Non-periodic Miura-Origami monocytes**
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Straight configuration Miura-Origami

Equivalent Poisson's ratio analysis

Planar unfolding state

Space folding state

- For same α , $\log_{10}(|v_{xy}|) \downarrow$ as $\theta \uparrow$
- $\log_{10}(|v_{xy}|) > 0$ when $\alpha < 45^\circ$
- When $\alpha > 45^\circ$, $\exists \theta \rightarrow \log_{10}(|v_{xy}|) < 0$

Straight configuration Miura-Origami

Equivalent Poisson's ratio analysis

- For same θ and α , $v_{xz} \gg v_{yz}$
- Both $v_{xz}, v_{yz} \rightarrow 0$ as $\theta \rightarrow 90^\circ$
- For same θ , $v_{xz}, v_{yz} \uparrow$ as $\alpha \uparrow$
- For same α , $v_{xz}, v_{yz} \downarrow$ as $\theta \uparrow$

Straight configuration Miura-Origami

Equivalent structural stiffness analysis

$m=1, n=1$

$m=3, n=4$

- Equivalent structural stiffness:

$$\bar{K}_x = -\frac{2n(2m-1)bk(\theta_0 - \theta) + 2m(2n-1)ak(\varphi_0 - \varphi) \frac{d\varphi}{d\theta}}{m^2 a^2 \sin^2 \alpha \cos \theta (\sin \theta - \sin \theta_0)}$$

$$\bar{K}_y = -\frac{2 \left[n(2m-1)bk(\theta_0 - \theta) + m(2n-1)ak(\varphi_0 - \varphi) \frac{d\varphi}{d\theta} \right] (1 - \sin^2 \alpha \sin^2 \theta)^{\frac{3}{2}}}{n^2 b^2 \sin^2 \alpha \cos \alpha \sin \theta \cos \theta \left(\frac{\cos \alpha}{\sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \alpha \sin^2 \theta}} - \frac{\cos \alpha}{\sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \alpha \sin^2 \theta_0}} \right)}$$

$$\bar{K}_z = \frac{8 \left[n(2m-1)bk(\theta_0 - \theta) + m(2n-1)ak(\varphi_0 - \varphi) \frac{d\varphi}{d\theta} \right] (1 - \sin^2 \alpha \sin^2 \theta)^{\frac{3}{2}}}{b^2 \sin^2 \alpha \cos^2 \alpha \sin \theta \left(\frac{\cos \theta}{\sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \alpha \sin^2 \theta}} - \frac{\cos \theta_0}{\sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \alpha \sin^2 \theta_0}} \right)}$$

The theoretical model agrees with the results of the finite element model

Arc configuration Miura-Origami

Equivalent Poisson's ratio analysis

Curvilinear configuration
Miura single cell structure

(a) $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \uparrow$ synchronously

In Figure (a):

- For same α_1, α_2 , $-\log_{10}(|v_{x\zeta}|) \uparrow$ as $\theta \uparrow$
- $-\log_{10}(|v_{x\zeta}|) \uparrow$ as $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \uparrow$ synchronously

In Figure (b):

- For same $\Delta\alpha$, $-\log_{10}(|v_{x\zeta}|) \uparrow$ as $\theta \uparrow$ in general. but when $\Delta\alpha >$ a threshold value, the sign of $v_{x\zeta}$ is changed.

(b) $\Delta\alpha = \alpha_2 - \alpha_1 \uparrow$

Arc configuration Miura-Origami

(a) $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \uparrow$ synchronously (b) $\Delta\alpha = \alpha_2 - \alpha_1 \uparrow$
 (c) $\alpha_1, \alpha_2 \uparrow$ synchronously (d) $\Delta\alpha = \alpha_2 - \alpha_1 \uparrow$

- In general, $\log_{10}(|v_{\rho\zeta}|), \log_{10}(|v_{\rho x}|) \uparrow$ as $\theta \uparrow$
- When $\alpha_1 \geq 55, \alpha_2 \geq 75^\circ$, the curve would show a negative Sharp Vertex, which means the sign of v is changed.
- When $\Delta\alpha = 55^\circ$, the curve of $\log_{10}(|v_{\rho\zeta}|)$ would show a positive Sharp Vertex, which means the deformation in ζ direction is changed from extension to Systolic. And when $\Delta\alpha = 75^\circ$, there will be another negative Sharp Vertex.
- When $\Delta\alpha = 55^\circ$, the curve of $\log_{10}(|v_{\rho x}|)$ would show a positive Sharp Vertex.

Arc configuration Miura-Origami

Equivalent structural stiffness analysis

$m=1, n=1$

$m=4, n=4$

- E is the total energy
- U is the total potential energy

$$E = U - \int_{\xi_0}^{\xi} f_x \frac{dL_x}{d\xi} d\xi - \int_{\xi_0}^{\xi} f_\zeta \frac{dL_\zeta}{d\xi} d\xi - \int_{\xi_0}^{\xi} f_\rho \frac{dL_\rho}{d\xi} d\xi$$

- Equivalent structural stiffness:

$$K_x = \frac{1}{(dL_x/d\theta)^3} \left(\frac{d^2U}{d\theta^2} \frac{dL_x}{d\theta} - \frac{dU}{d\theta} \frac{d^2L_x}{d\theta^2} \right)$$

The theoretical model agrees with the results of the finite element model

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 - Parametric modeling
 - FEM Structural analysis
 - Aerodynamic analysis
- **Conclusions**

Parametric modeling

2D Pattern Inverse Problem Design

Geometric Transformation of Origami Surfaces with Inhomogeneous Curvature

(1) Co-linearity constraint

(2) Parallel constraint

$$A_i A_{i+1} // B_i B_{i+1} // B'_i B'_{i+1}$$

(3) Symmetry constraint

B_i and B'_i are symmetric about $A_i A_{i+1}$

$$\textcircled{1} A_1 = (0,0),$$

$$\textcircled{2} B_1 = \left(\frac{a_1}{\sqrt{k_{S1}+1}}, \frac{k_{S1}a_1}{\sqrt{k_{S1}+1}} \right)$$

$$\textcircled{3} A_2 = \left(\frac{\sin(\alpha_1) \cdot \cos(\arctan(k_{S1}) + \alpha_1)}{h}, \frac{\sin(\alpha_1) \cdot \sin(\arctan(k_{S1}) + \alpha_1)}{h} \right),$$

$$\textcircled{4} B_2 = \left(A_2(x) + \frac{a_1}{\sqrt{k_{S1}+1}}, A_2(y) + \frac{k_{S1}a_1}{\sqrt{k_{S1}+1}} \right)$$

⑤ Calculate A_3, B_3 by

$$\frac{1/k_{A_{i+1}B_{i+1}} - k_{A_i A_{i+1}}}{1 + k_{A_i A_{i+1}} / k_{A_{i+1}B_{i+1}}} = \frac{k_{B_{i+1}B_{i+2}} - 1/k_{A_{i+1}B_{i+1}}}{1 + k_{A_i A_{i+1}} / k_{A_{i+1}B_{i+2}}} \quad (i = 1, 2, 3 \dots)$$

⑥ Calculate B'_1, B'_2, B'_3 by Symmetry

⑦ Go to ②

Realize the establishment of an origami model for **any zero-Gaussian curvature** surface.

Parametric modeling

ABAQUS python Secondary development script modeling

NACA0012 Miura-origami skin

Structural analysis

load capacity analysis

The load capacity of the Miura-Origami skin was investigated by FEM software. A uniform pressure was set to the skin. And the 4 different skin under 3 different skin wide cases were simulated.

Different feature sizes Miura-Origami skin

Structural analysis

load capacity analysis

- The Miura skin's deformation is negatively correlated with the cell size.
- The Miura skin shows more advantages when the width is small.
- Comprehensive considerate of in-plane deformation, out-plane load bearing and structural strength, the **Miura_10 at 100/200mm width** is a **better** choice for morphing skin.

Skin mode	Max.Ux	Max.Uy	Max.Uz	Max.Von-Mises
100mm Width				
Miura_05	0.152	0.087	1.108	67.56
Miura_10	0.056	0.034	0.209	62.28
Miura_15	0.068	0.035	0.18	105.09
Smooth	0.142	0.008	1.529	96.39
200mm Width				
Miura_05	0.450	0.368	8.101	348.66
Miura_10	0.383	0.275	3.420	260.71
Miura_15	0.276	0.218	1.818	228.73
Smooth	0.752	0.066	5.212	234.07
300mm Width				
Miura_05	0.810	0.706	16.460	429.22
Miura_10	0.661	0.690	12.230	485.26
Miura_15	0.611	0.592	7.208	485.18
Smooth	1.388	0.158	9.198	298.96

Structural analysis

load capacity analysis

For Miura_10 skin, the load capacity of different half-collapse angle θ were investigated. And the smooth skin is also added for comparison.

Skin size	Max.Ux	Max.Uy	Max.Uz	Max.Von-Mises
$\theta = 15^\circ$	0.540	1.972	21.49	429.65
$\theta = 30^\circ$	0.341	0.994	11.73	508.14
$\theta = 45^\circ$	0.383	0.275	3.420	500.31
$\theta = 60^\circ$	0.398	0.230	3.034	334.24
$\theta = 75^\circ$	0.219	0.077	1.010	201.15
Smooth	0.752	0.066	5.212	234.07

- The deformation goes down as θ increases.
- The Max. Ux of Miura skin is smaller than the smooth skin while the Max. Uy is bigger. But the difference is more significant.
- The Max. Ux of Miura skin is smaller than the smooth skin when $\theta \geq 45^\circ$
- The stress of Miura skin gets smaller when θ increases, and becomes smaller than smooth skin when $\theta \geq 75^\circ$

Structural analysis

Tension, compression, bending deformation

Deformation capacity of the skin under tensile, compressive and bending loads are investigated. The results are shown below. For comparison, F/F_{Ref} is calculated. The F is the reaction force of this Miura case, and the F_{Ref} is the reaction force of smooth skin under unit load.

- For same width, the smaller the cell size of Miura is, the greater the in-plane stiffness is.
- For same width, the cell size shows insignificant effect to out-plane stiffness.
- At the same load, wider skin makes bigger deformation.

Structural analysis

Tension, compression, bending deformation

Tension

Compression

Bending

- The smaller the θ , the stronger the skin deformation ability
- When θ is small, the curve is linear. When θ gets bigger, the linear relationship gets weaker.

The results show that by **adjusting the geometric parameters** of the Miura-Ori unit cell, **the in-plane/out-of-plane stiffness of the structure can be adjusted**, so that the anisotropic Miura-Ori skin structure has both **out-of-plane bearing and in-plane deformation** capabilities.

Aerodynamic analysis

Using FLUENT to calculate the aerodynamic performance. The size of Miura skin is Miura_10, θ is 30° , width is 100mm. Two different speed (0.1Ma and 0.6Ma) cases are calculated and the smooth wing skin cases are also run for comparison.

Aerodynamic analysis

- At low speed, the drag of Miura is a bit of bigger than smooth wing. And the lift is also larger. The Lift-to-drag ratio line is almost coincide.
- At high speed, when the attack angle is bigger than 5°, the Lift-to-drag ratio drops quickly.

The aerodynamic analysis shows that at low speed, the Miura-Origami skin has **limited influence** to the aerodynamic performance than smooth skin .

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Conclusions

- ◆ The Miura-Origami theoretical model is developed. The theoretical expressions for **Poisson's ratio** and **equivalent stiffness** of Miura-Ori structure **in linear/arc configuration** are derived, and the effects of Miura-Ori structural parameters on the mechanical properties are analyzed.
- ◆ The method of Miura-Origami **parametric modeling** is developed.
- ◆ The **bear** and **deform** capacity are investigated. The results show that by **adjusting** the **geometric parameters** of the Miura-Ori unit cell, the in-plane/out-of-plane **mechanical properties** of the structure can be **programmed**.
- ◆ The aerodynamic analysis is taken. The result shows that at low speed, the Miura-Origami skin has **limited influence (less than 1%)** to the aerodynamic performance than smooth skin .

**Thanks for
your attention**

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